

Measurement of Foot Arch Height During Gait Using Smartphones or Action Cameras

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Abstract: Foot arch problems, such as flatfoot and high & rigid arches, are common and such issues cause symptoms such as Hallux Valgus, plantar fascia, and calcaneal spur as they decrease impact absorbance, walking endurance, and balance. It is difficult to measure movement and deformities, such as the medial longitudinal arch height and rearfoot (calcaneal) angle, as they quickly change during gait. Typically, these issues have been diagnosed by podiatrists when the patient is standing still or by naked eye observance.

In this study, we developed a point-of-care computer vision-based bone marker tracking system that can be used with a common smartphone or action camera. Using this system, podiatrists could quantitatively identify bone or joint movement issues and deformities during gait. The effects of prescribed insoles are also quantitatively validated using this system. In flatfoot subjects, the arch angle increased by 10%. Additionally, the reactive control of arches in high and rigid-arch subjects was improved.

Keywords: Image-based tracking; smartphone; action cameras; gait

I. INTRODUCTION

Feet have very complicated structures as they contain complex bones, ligaments, and joints that work mechanically [1].

Less functional feet are often unable to correctly absorb shock or not maintain the driving force during walking. Generally, feet fall into three types, i.e., normal feet, flat feet, and high and rigid-arched feet.

Low-arch flat feet tend to cause Hallux Valgus (HV), Pes Latus (broad foot), and Pes Planus (flat feet). The diagnosis and correction of these common problems are as follows: HV is quite common, with 23% of the population under the age of 65, and 35% of the population over 65 having HV [2]. HV is diagnosed by measuring the deformity of the HV and M1M2 angle. An orthosis or supporter is commonly used to correct HV. Pes Latus is typically diagnosed based on the footprint pattern, and is treated using insoles with a metatarsal dome. Arch support insoles are a standard correction for Pes Planus.

Feet with higher arches are commonly less flexible, causing under-pronation during the stance phase of gait. Low-arch flatfeet and high-arch rigid feet have issues with impact absorbance. Absorbing impacts is vital for

maintaining a stable gait and long-range walking.

Observing and examining foot flexibility is difficult due to the rapid velocity at which feet hit the floor during walking, and the standard frame-rate of video cameras (30 or 60 frame/sec) is too slow to capture foot movement. It is also very difficult to observe foot warping and movement during gait, even for trained podiatrists.

Humans have approximately 206 bones in their bodies. One foot has 26 bones; therefore, both feet contain almost a quarter of all bones in the body. The foot moves in all three planes, i.e., the frontal, sagittal, and transversal planes, in a complicated manner and can be separated into fore, middle, and rear parts. These parts are moved and warped through muscle tension and the ground reaction force during gait.

The medial longitudinal arch (MLA) influences shock absorption and the driving force to the body. Its alignment influences its height, and it is also reduced by pronated foot and HV. A lower MLA reduces stability and is a risk factor for lower extremity injuries.

Hyper-pronation observed at stand-still is related to lower limb such as plantar fasciitis, metatarsal bone and/or tibial stress fractures, and patellofemoral pain

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syndrome, and it also causes overuse injuries, such as medial tibial stress syndrome [3-6].

The arch height index and navicular drop are often used for MLA classification during clinical foot arch structure evaluations [7-11]. Kim [12] stated that “when the MLA has descended or has been completely lost leading to structural or functional deformation, the ability to absorb impacts will decrease, and the sense of balance will be lost so that stability decreased during walking or running leading to walking difficulties and endurance decreases.”

Fig. 1 Bone structure of the human foot

During gait, dorsiflexion to plantar flexion of the foot passively occurs at heel contact due to the ground reaction force. Simultaneously, weight is applied to the medial arch, causing the arch height to decrease. Ligaments and muscles prevent the lowering of the foot arch. This process absorbs shock when the arch is slightly stretched. The foot sole contact area is largest when the lower limb passes the vertical line.

Abnormal foot posture is related to the biomechanical dysfunction of the lower leg and various overuse injuries [13]. Several measurements are used for diagnosis, such as the longitudinal arch angle, foot posture index, arch height index, and navicular drop and drift, which can be used to infer rearfoot motion during gait. Although these measurements have been well-examined, they are not direct observations of the dynamics of gait. Nevertheless, it has been reported that static measurements do not consistently predict the dynamic rearfoot motion in the stance phase [13]. Feet with normal flexibility can walk on uneven grounds, while less flexible feet are unable to contend with such conditions, thereby causing leg pain and dysfunctions.

It is difficult to measure the movement and deformity of the foot in detail as they rapidly change during gait. Issues are commonly diagnosed when the

patient is standing still or through naked-eye observance by a podiatrist. Custom-made insoles are often prescribed; however, it is also difficult to objectively evaluate insoles.

Motion capture systems are already widely used in many rehabilitation fields. However, there are two significant difficulties relating to their use. The musculoskeletal structure of feet and their movement are highly complicated. To capture the movement and deformity of the foot, numerous markers in small places are required. The analysis of the captured data is also time-consuming. The movement and deformation speed of the foot during the gait process poses another difficulty. Standard motion-capture systems have cameras that can capture 100–120 frames per second, which is sufficient to capture the movements of natural extremities, but too slow to record the foot movements in detail, particularly between heel contact and mid-stance. These periods are indispensable for diagnosing foot arch problems.

Recently, smartphones and action cameras have become able to record 240 frame/sec movies in full high-definition (HD; 1920 × 1080) or 720p (1280 × 720). Theoretically, this frame rate is sufficient to capture foot details during gait. Computer vision-based tracking techniques have also been dramatically improved by GPU computing.

In this study, we developed a computer vision-based bone marker-tracking system to be used at the point-of-care that can be used with a common smartphone or action camera. Using this system, podiatrists could quantitatively identify bone or joint movement problems and deformities during gait. The effects of the prescribed insoles are also quantitatively validated using this system.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Measurement problems and solution

It is difficult to measure the movement and deformities of the foot in detail as their changes during gait are rapid. These issues are typically diagnosed at stand-still posture or by naked-eye observance by a podiatrist. Custom-made insoles have typically been prescribed to treat such issues. However, it is also difficult to objectively evaluate such insoles.

Motion-capture systems are already widely used in many rehabilitation fields. However, there are two significant difficulties associated with such systems.

First, the musculoskeletal structure and movement of the foot are extremely complicated, and a large number of markers in small places are required to capture the movement and deformity of the foot. The analysis of such data is also highly time-consuming. Another difficulty is the movement and deformation speed of the foot during gait. The cameras in standard motion-capture systems can capture 100–120 frames per second, which is sufficient to capture the movements of extremities, but insufficient to capture detailed foot movements, particularly between heel contact and the mid-stance stage. This period is vital when diagnosing foot arch problems.

Recently, smartphones and action cameras have become able to record 240 frame/sec movies in full HD (1920 × 1080) or 720p (1280 × 720) resolution. Theoretically, this is sufficient to capture detailed foot movements during gait. Computer vision-based tracking techniques have also been greatly improved by GPU computing.

In this study, we developed a computer vision-based bone marker-tracking system for point-of-care use that can be used with common smartphone or action cameras. Using this system, podiatrists could quantitatively identify bone or joint movement problems and deformities during gait. The effects of the prescribed insoles are also quantitatively validated using this system.

B. Gait video capture

Measurement and analysis involve the following: capturing videos of gait using consumer devices with cameras, such as smartphones or action cameras, and the tracking of joint markers using our image analysis system.

The participants were asked to walk on a treadmill. Three markers, which were small (5 mm diameter) paper stickers, were attached to the 1. proximal point above the navicular bone (medial border), 2. medial calcaneus (20 mm in front of the most protruding part of the calcaneus on the sagittal plane and 10 mm above the ground), and 3. medial of the first metatarsal head. Navicular point are referenced Chuter (2010).

A GoPro 7 Black (GoPro Inc.) camera was used to capture videos of the gait up-close at 240 frames/sec with 1280 × 960 pixels. From our trials, 240 minimum required frame-rate for automatically tracking foot details.

The cameras were placed 30 cm from the target foot

in the midstance phase. During all trials, the same relative camera angle to the gait cadence was used.

The gait speed was 1.7 km per hour. The gaits were recorded from five to twenty cadences after the subjects had become accustomed to the speed of the treadmill. Therefore, stable gaits were tracked and analysed.

Fig. 2 Marker positions

C. Tracking system

The marker-tracking software was developed based on OpenCV 4.1.0 [14] in Python 3.6.

The initial tracking areas were manually set on the screen by watching the captured 240-fps videos in slow-motion. A cross-hair range-setter was used to assign markers and their neighbouring tracking areas. Tracking started before heel contact, and ended during the midstance phase.

Fig. 3 Tracking markers just before heel contact.

III. RESULTS

A. Participants

Ten university students participated in this study; some had rigid and high arches, some had normal feet, and some had flat feet (average age: 21.33 years old, SD=0.62 years; sex ratio: nine males, three females). None of the subjects had any gait disorders.

B. Measurement results in all subjects

Fig.4 shows the measurement results for all subjects which are barefoot condition. The graph shows the angle of markers, as shown in fig. 6. The timeline (x-axis) of fig. 4 starts from the time of heel contact of all subjects (Table.1).

Subjects #1, 7 and 8 are classified Normal foot as diagnostic classification. Subjects #2, 4,5 and 6 are classified flat foot. Subjects #3, 9 and 10 are classified rigid and high-arch. Subjects #3 has normal arch but rigid.

Measured arch angles seem no consistent relations between subject's sex and weight. Subjects #5, 6 and 10 are females and belongs to different classes.

Subject weight also seems not related to diagnostic classes. Subjects #1, 7 and 9 have relatively heavier weight. Subjects #6 and 10 have light weight.

Fig. 4 Measurement results for all subjects

In below lines, three typical patterns of foot arch are shown (Normal foot gait, Flat foot gait, Rigid and high-arch case). These types correspond to the classification which has been used for diagnosis of podiatrists. With applying wedge insoles, the arch angle improvements are also shown.

Table.1 Details regarding the subjects

Subject #	Sex	Weight (kg)
1	Male	75
2	Male	62
3	Male	65
4	Male	61
5	Female	60
6	Female	49
7	Male	70
8	Male	65
9	Male	70
10	Female	45

C. Normal foot gait

Fig.5 shows the coordinates of the markers just before heel contact and defines the angle between the navicular bone (marker 1) – medial calcaneus, (2) – medial of the first metatarsal base, and (3) the height of the triangle.

Fig.6 shows the angle of the 1-2-3 transition. Until the 43rd frame, the left foot was in the swing phase, and, therefore, off the ground. Before the 50th frame, the angle surges, indicating that the foot arch closes 2° at the heel contact and preparation for impact. Near the 60th frame, the arch opens by 2°, and the open arch can absorb the reaction force. The arch then recovers to 23° during the mid-stance phase.

This subject does not have a perfect gait. The forefoot has small Varus (rotated towards the midline) that could cause a small amount of late pronation. The effect of this small displacement requires further investigation.

Fig. 5 Coordinates of the tracked markers (pixels) just before heel contact

Fig. 6 Angle 1-2-3: navicular bone (marker 1) – medial calcaneus, (2) – medial of the first metatarsal base, (3) and height of the triangle

Fig. 7 Angle 1-2-3 for a subject with normal feet

D. Flat-foot gait

For the subjects with flat feet and rigid & high arches, we created wedge insoles using high-density

hard urethane with an angle of 10° and inserted them beneath the heel (Fig.8).

Fig. 8 Wedge insole (10°)

Fig.9a shows the angle 1-2-3 of the gait of a subject with flat feet in 0.5 sec, or 120 frames. From beginning to the 45th frame (just before heel contact), the angle was 22 to 21.5° . Following heel contact, the angle decreased by 3° to 19° .

Fig.8b shows the movement with the wedge. Just before heel contact, the angle was 24.5° , which is an increase of $2-3^\circ$ increased. During the mid-stance phase, the angle increased by 2.5° to 21.5° . Therefore, the foot arch was increased by approximately 10% with the addition of the wedge.

The subtalar joint is one of the structures of the foot., which consists of the talus and calcaneus. This structure acts as a functional joint and a mechanical link between the foot and lower extremity. Kirby mentioned that the spatial location of the subtalar joint axis affects the pronation and supination moments, and also the functioning of the foot [15-17]. The subtalar joint undergoes pronation and supination during the walking cycle. During gait, the foot alternates between acting as a mobile adaptor and rigid lever under the pronation and supination motions in the order given.

Between the loading response and mid-stance phases, to allow the pronate to work as a mobile adaptor, it adjusts to alterations in the ground surface and functions as part of the shock-absorption mechanism (looser joint). Between the terminal stance and pre-swing phases, to allow supination, the foot acts as a rigid lever, which reduces the stability of the sagittal plane of the foot during the propulsive phase of gait (tighter joints) [18].

Placing a medial wedge beneath the heel reduced

the pronation moment across the subtalar joint, and also increased the supination moment. Therefore, the height of the navicular changed less during weight-bearing with a wedge than without. By allowing the drop of the scaphoid bone to rest, the foot can enter pronation and gain propulsion at the terminal stance.

Fig. 9(a) Angle 1-2-3 of a flat-footed subject without a wedge

Fig. 9(b) Angle 1-2-3 of a flat-footed subject with a wedge

E. Rigid and high-arch case

Fig.10a shows the angle 1-2-3 of the gait of a subject with rigid & high-arch feet. From the beginning of the swing phase to the heel-contact and mid-stance phases, the angle only changed by 1°. This suggests that the arch was rigid and impact absorbance was poor.

Fig.10b shows the angle after providing the subject with the wedge. Before heel-contact, the arch increased by 2°, and then decreased by 3° after heel-contact. Therefore, the foot arch became more flexible and the effect of the wedge is significant.

Fig. 10(a) Angle 1-2-3 of a subject with rigid & high-arch feet without a wedge

Fig. 10(b) Angle 1-2-3 of a subject with rigid & high-arch feet with a wedge

III. DISCUSSION

There are several approaches to treating flat feet. The navicular bone and sustentaculum tali are the primary targets for insoles. In many cases of flat feet, the calcaneal bone pronates (rotates inward), the astragalus (anklebone), which is part of the subtalar joint, rotates inward (medial rotation) and plantarflexes. Finally, the height of the foot arch is lowered.

In this study, a wedged insole was applied to the sustentaculum tali. Medial wedges are commonly placed beneath the heel. We observed that the medial wedge reduces the pronation moment of the calcaneal bone and then prevents the dropping of the foot arch.

Foot arch stiffness is commonly assessed under static alignments, such as standstill or sitting postures. However, gait is dynamic, and the properties of feet differ physically in terms of their skeletomuscular structure and dynamics.

In this study, changes in the angle of the foot arch during gait were successfully measured using common smartphones or action cameras. We also validated the effectiveness of using a wedged insole to treat flat and rigid high-arched feet. Based on the mechanics causing flatfoot, we measured the movement of the navicular bone in three dimensions.

During general diagnosis, assessors begin an interview and palpate the foot of the patient. Many foot problems are initially treated with a wedge, excluding contracture and diabetes. If the patient received their diagnosis from an assessor with little experience or static measurements, it could be difficult to provide them with an effectual and suitable cure. This study showed that, in some cases., wedges should be suitable if the static measurements detected the foot type or characteristics. However, some wedges do not affect the arches of subjects. This does not mean that static measurements are not useful; rather, feet are highly complicated and considerable experience is required to properly evaluate them. Our system could assist assessors with little experience and those with considerable experience to verify the effects of treatment. Our results suggested that the approach can be used for closely examining treatments.

Subjects with arches lowered by mid or forefoot conditions could be distinguished by adding a camera behind the foot. Additionally, this study could not capture the whole gait cycle of the subjects, as the length of the videos was limited by technical problems. We are developing a camera synchronisation system that could capture a wider video area to resolve this issue. The system could capture the frame in which the arch receives most stress when the legs are crossed from the sagittal view. Our study has several strengths, as it demonstrated that smartphones and action cameras can track markers and produce detailed results without expensive machinery.

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